

Future Marketing Strategies

S.Parasuraman

*Research Scholar (FT), PG & Research Department of Commerce
Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Arts and Science, Dharmapuri
Periyar University, Tamil Nadu, India*

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 6

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2018

ISSN: 2320-4168

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Parasuraman, S & Sathya, N. "Future Marketing Strategies." *Shanlax International Journal of Commerce*, vol. 6, no. S1, 2018, pp. 311–316.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1461528>

Dr.N.Sathya

*Assistant Professor, PG & Research Department of Commerce
Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Arts and Science, Dharmapuri
Periyar University, Tamil Nadu, India*

Abstract

The Marketing is a key aspect of any business. It not only showcases your product or service in the target market to put your prospective customers in the know of your offering, but it also helps survive in highly competitive markets which constantly witness the change in trends. That's why marketing strategy also requires change. Often it is the marketing strategy which is known to have changed the market trends. It can't achieve such results unless it keeps one eye on the present and the other on future. The marketing tribe is utterly down-to-earth. They are all the time focused on consumer psychology. Therefore, they never lag behind in finding out innovative ways to attract more customers to use their products or services. This article explains how to create the marketing strategies, implementing process and monitor its effectiveness.

Keywords: Marketing Strategies, Marketing Process, and Marketing Tribe

Future Marketing Strategy

The following are some emerging marketing trends which are going to rule the future of marketing.

Making Use of the State-of-the-Art Gadgets that have Changed Life and Consumer Habits

This is important. Life is made increasingly easy and, at the same time, efficient with state-of-the-art gadgets. One of these is, undoubtedly, mobile devices (such as mobiles, smart phones, tablets, etc.) of which utility is astoundingly diversified by a burst of applications. The apps of Flipkart, Amazon, etc. provide a good case in point. The whole world is moving fast and whatever is to be done is to be done on the go. That's what people are doing. Their attention span is very small and nothing that fails to interest them, at first sight, is sure to fail in commanding their affection. Here's where mobile devices come in for good. Just imagine how many mobile alerts you receive on the hourly basis, and how many of them are promotional. These promotions bring you vis-à-vis an infinite variety of choice of consumer goods and services. Therefore, the whole world has gone mobile, know the potential of your mobile device.

Building Relationship with Customers

The customer is the king' has been a dominating marketing mantra since quite some time now. But every person is a prospective consumer and each person is different from the other, and so the customer has his criteria in choosing what is to be consumed. Marketing does offer them some options to choose from. But the known tendency of customers is to try out different options until they find out what suits them most. And when they find this out, they stick to it. In other words, they become loyal to the brand that wins them.

The market research, therefore, is the place where it all begins. It's based on the market research that products or services are designed. The final phase of the marketing labor is to advertise them to the target markets. All activities on the part of a business end here. From this point onwards, all eyes are on the customers. If they pass a product or service, the foundation of the relationship between a brand and its customers is laid. Businesses need must build on it by upgrading their product or service. If they don't do this, their competitors surely will make deep inroads into their hard-won market. That's why businesses are always keen to know what their customers have to say about their offerings.

User-Generated and Fresh Content (UGC)

The mushrooming e-commerce businesses all over the world bring to our attention a new marketing phenomenon called user-generated content (UGC). This is called online customer reviews. Similar content is found on so many social media out there, in pictures, videos, and also in blogs and guest posts, whether it is a corporate blog or a blog of some small business.

According to Facebook white paper statistics, every day 350 million photos are uploaded on Facebook, more than 500 tweets are registered on Twitter, and around 12 million videos are shared on Vine. So much more must be transpiring on other social networking sites is only a matter of conjecture. The reason these are proving extremely effective is that they are there to show to the consumers that the concerned product or service is tried and not found wanting in any respect. Consumers' views hold more authenticity for consumers than advertisements. This gives the fair indication of how brands and consumers are moving closer to mutually create a viable marketing strategy for mutual benefit. Very often customers also get the reward for promoting a brand through his feedback. That is what was meant by mutual benefit. This tactic is extremely valuable to build up a society of loyal or returning customers.

Effective Use of Social Media

Apart from what the users generate, the social media tools also help businesses do their bit with their help. If marketing is done effectively on social networking sites like Facebook and Twitter, it has the potential to generate revenue there and then. Take, for instance, a new and extremely exhilarating feature that Facebook has come up with. It's about boosting money transfer free-of-charge. Now consumers can save their credit card details on Facebook, which allows them to access as many as 450,000 e-commerce businesses out there. If they find something that interests them, they can buy it right there. Especially interesting from customers' point-of-view is the 'free-of-charge' tag attached to this system. If they do money transfer here, they don't incur processing fees. Other money transfer means do entail processing charges. This is going to make big difference for the businesses in the time to come - the 'Buy' button coming up on Facebook and Twitter.

Brand Earns the Customers

No matter how vehemently you market your goods, if they are not worth the marketing campaign, they are not going to last. There are other competitors in the market who are going to overtake

your product or service. Ultimately, quality will speak for itself when customers use your product. So, you will never be able to place your product in the minds of the customers until and unless the product proves good when they use it. It builds credit for your business. That's how Apple, Amazon, Microsoft, etc. are the brands which will constantly beg respect from their worldwide clientele. Their research labs are working all the time to innovate their products and services.

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats) analysis a very commonly used strategic framework in marketing. It is simple to understand and provides a great starting point for considering strategic choices. A SWOT analysis is also versatile, as it can be applied to a marketing product, business unit or entire company about strategic business goals. A SWOT analysis has two key purposes:

- To help a company to determine its strategic goals
- To provide the foundation for developing a strategy

Strengths (S)

Strengths are the factors that are going to help you get better results. The company will do well if you can base your strategy around these things. Strength is an internal factor. This means you can control it. Things like resources, investment, and skilled labor are considered strengths. In SWOT analysis in marketing, you will consider the following things as your strength:

Brand Recognition: The company product is well known by the people then it can act as the strength for marketing strategy. The customers can use its name and recognition to advertize your products for sale.

Locations of the Business: The company or shop is located in the city center then you are likely to have a very good business. It makes it convenient for the customers to be able to visit your shop. This is a big strength that you may have over your competitors.

Specialist in Marketing Expertise: When you have an expert in marketing then the company can develop a marketing strategy quite easily. He/she will have the required experience to form strategies based on experience. This is a massive boost when doing a SWOT analysis in marketing.

Introducing Something New: What better way to capture the market than providing newer products? If your firm can come up with new ideas, then your marketing strategy will be based on innovation and novelty.

Weaknesses (W)

Weaknesses are also internal factors that will derail you from making progress. When doing a SWOT analysis in marketing, we need to consider which things will make your marketing strategy look weak and unconvincing. The following factors can be called weaknesses:

Poor Distribution: If we have a poor distribution channel for your products then you are likely to suffer. If the customers are not getting your products on time or even on the market, then that's an obstacle for your marketing strategy.

Not Distinguishable Feature: We cannot stand out in the market if your products are no different from the rest of the competitors and we need to have your signature or an identity.

Lack of Online Presence: In the modern era, online marketing is a key way to grab the customer's attention. If we are not doing enough online, then you cannot succeed well.

Opportunities (O)

SWOT analysis in marketing will look at almost everything as an opportunity. This is because you never know what events or situations you can use as a marketing weapon. Things such as:

Advancement in Technology: If the company buys newer technology. Or they come across newer ways to produce goods then that can be termed as an opportunity. This will help the company to strategize differently.

Increase in Demand: A situation may arise when the demand for your goods may increase both locally and internationally. If that happens, then you need to seize the opportunity. We can advertize the fact that your good is wanted abroad and thus create a brand name for yourself. This is smart marketing.

Social Events: Nothing increases the demand for certain goods like social events. Gift items become hot in demand during Christmas. Fireworks are sold every minute day before New Year's Eve. So when such an opportunity is opened up, the marketing strategy should be to take full advantage of the situation. Offer those discounts and other benefits so that your product is sold more.

Threats (T)

While doing a SWOT analysis in marketing, we have to be very careful regarding the situations that will hamper your marketing strategy. These situations are known as threats. Threats develop come out of nowhere. So it is better to identify them as soon as possible. That way the SWOT analysis in marketing will have a contingency plan to thwart the threat. The following conditions can be considered as a threat:

Competitors' Lower Price: This has to be the toughest threat to deal with. If your competitor lowers the price of their product, then there are very few things you can do about it. People are always likely to go for things that are less expensive. However if your SWOT analysis in marketing has this noted down, then you are likely to have a backup plan for it. Offering better quality or promotional offers may help.

Changes in Consumer Choice: If consumers all of a sudden decide to change their choice then you are likely to be in trouble. Fashion trends are always going to change, and this becomes a threat if you are producing the same kind of goods or services.

Economic Condition: Inflation, exchange rates, taxes and so on are all economic factors. If these things change too often, then your company will be affected negatively. Doing a SWOT analysis in marketing will require you to keep such things on mind and come up ways to avoid them.

Marketing Flowchart

A marketing flowchart is used to assure the clear presentation of the processes that are needed to be done for a specific marketing activity of the company. It serves as a visual plot of the marketing functions and the steps that are needed to be done to assure the quality of the final marketing material. The process of creating a marketing flowchart includes the design of the marketing program, the creation of budget and distribution plans, the steps that are needed to be followed in creating a specific marketing campaign, and the expected result of the marketing output.

The following points need to be considered while creating a marketing flowchart:

The input of information is very important as it allows the people involved in the marketing processes to know the items that they need to be aware of. The first thing to do is to conduct quality research with regards to the current marketing programs of the company and how can it be

improved by applying the processes that are involved in the marketing flowchart. A marketing plan also needs to consider the target market of the company. The flowchart to be done needs to showcase the market segment that a company needs to reach and other market areas that are needed to be penetrated by the business.

Customer motivation is also needed to be included in the marketing plan flow chart as it will help in maintaining or improving the purchasing activities and buying movement of consumers.

The objectives of the marketing plan must also be shown in the flow chart. This includes the expected output of the marketing program about finances, marketing activities, and the customers to be tapped.

Marketing strategies must also be relayed so that they can be tested for their efficiency and how they can give more sales to the company.

The elements of the marketing must be reviewed and considered as it allows the company to identify the links between the products and services that they offer the consumers, the advertising and promotion of the products and/or services, the price of the offerings of the business, and the place where these items are available for purchase or usage.

Finally, the result of the entire marketing program flow must be measured and must be subjected for another quality research or review to indicate whether it is helpful or not.

Figure 1 Marketing Flow Chart

Marketing flowcharts, once fully developed, can organize alternate paths which may be used should some functions and marketing actions not work well. And identifies decision points, and it also enlists the consequences or advantages of selecting a specific marketing option. It prevents errors and mishaps to occur especially that all the steps are enumerated and well thought of. It specifically presents all the steps that are needed to be followed in any marketing activities.

Conclusion

From the brief discussion above, of the viable strategies which are going to work in the time to come, we can clearly see that marketing is not a way to foist things on simple customers but rather an exercise directed to find ways to reach prospective customers and convince them about the utility of your product and service, effectively showcase your offerings, keep the target market well-informed about what is special about their offerings that sells, sustain a loyal clientele as well as increase it through serving their interests in ways discussed above. Here, it must be acknowledged that this discussion is not comprehensive. There are other marketing strategies as well, but they are beyond the scope of this article. Nevertheless, the strategies discussed here are broadly in use now and on which future strategies are going to be based.

References

- http://2013.igem.org/Team:British_Columbia/marketing
<http://pestleanalysis.com/swot-analysis-in-marketing/>
<http://www.businessdictionary.com/article/632/using-swot-analysis-to-develop-a-marketing-strategy/>
<http://www.marketingprofs.com/3/kyle1.asp>
<https://blog.fit4market.com/how-to-create-a-swot-analysis-for-developing-a-marketing-plan>
<https://smallbusiness.chron.com/swot-analysis-marketing-strategy-5071.html>
<https://www.business2community.com/small-business/plan-future-business-swot-analysis-0867032>
<https://www.entrepreneur.com/article/300473>
<https://www.forbes.com/sites/steveolenski/2018/03/29/is-it-possible-to-future-proof-your-marketing-strategy/#3c5b04563a4b>
<https://www.marsdd.com/mars-library/swot-analysis-a-framework-to-develop-strategic-marketing-and-business-goals/>
<https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/marketing-and-sales/our-insights/the-future-of-marketing>
<https://www.socialmediatoday.com/marketing/5-strategies-will-govern-future-marketing>

Web Sources

- <http://pestleanalysis.com/swot-analysis-in-marketing/>
<https://www.socialmediatoday.com/marketing/5-strategies-will-govern-future-marketing>
<https://www.template.net/business/charts/marketing-flow-chart-template/>